

An Observational Study Correlating the Modified Tardieu Scale and Hmax/Mmax Ratio to Evaluate Wrist Flexor Spasticity in Chronic Stroke Patients

Chirag Chabhadiya¹, Deepak Lohar², Jafar Khan³

¹Department of Physiotherapy, Pacific College of Physiotherapy, Udaipur

²Associate Professor of Neurological and Psychosomatic Disorder Department of Physiotherapy Pacific College of Physiotherapy, Udaipur, Rajasthan

³Dean and HOD Pacific College of Physiotherapy, Pacific Medical University, Udaipur, Rajasthan

Received: 25-05-2024 / Revised: 23-06-2024 / Accepted: 26-07-2024

Corresponding Author: Dr. Chirag Chabhadiya

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Stroke is one of the most commonly occurring disease which leads to hemiparesis along with other symptoms like spasticity, sensory disturbances etc. considered to be a part of positive signs of upper motor neuron (UMN) syndrome. The aim of the present study was to co-relate the MTS and Hmax/Mmax ratio in the assessment of wrist flexors spasticity in the patients with chronic stroke. It was an observational study which consisted of 32 chronic stroke patients. Both male and female with age group 35-70 years and stroke duration more than 3 months were included in the study. After the approval for the study from the ethical committee, 32 stroke subjects who were diagnosed as having spasticity of wrist flexors of upper limb were selected for the study who fulfilled the inclusion and exclusion criteria and written consent was taken who were willing to participate in the study. All the measurements have been taken in morning hours between 9:00 to 12:00am. To see the effect of spasticity on Hmax/Mmax ratio, Hmax/Mmax ratio was taken in 33 normal individuals also in same age group under similar testing conditions. Statistical analysis was done using SPSS 14for windows. The correlation between Hmax/Mmax ratio and dynamic angle component of Modified Tardieu Scale (MTS) were evaluated using Pearson's correlation coefficient test. Similarly, correlation between Hmax/Mmax ratio and quality of muscle reaction component of Modified Tardieu Scale (MTS) was evaluated using Spearman's correlation coefficient test. It was suggestive of moderately negative correlation($r=-0.308$) between Dynamic angle component of Modified Tardieu Scale and Hmax/Mmax ratio. And moderately positive correlation($r=0.338$) between Quality of muscle reaction component of Modified Tardieu Scale and Hmax/Mmax ratio. And comparison between Hmax/Mmax ratio of stroke patients and normal individuals was done using unpaired-t test, which suggested that there was statistically significant increase in Hmax/Mmax ratio in stroke patients ($t=3.517$, $p=0.001$) so, the result of the present study rejects the null hypothesis. So, it can be concluded that MTS and Hmax/Mmax ratio can reliably use in the assessment of wrist flexors spasticity in the patients with chronic stroke. And it is also providing good electrophysiological evidence to assess wrist flexors spasticity in chronic stroke patients.

Keywords: Chronic Stroke, Spasticity, Modified Tardieu scale, Hmax/Mmax ratio.

This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.

Introduction

Stroke is defined as sudden loss of neurological functions resulting from ischemic or haemorrhagic lesions in the brain, which lasts more than 24 hours. It is caused by interruption of blood flow to the brain usually by atherosclerotic plaques that occur at certain sites of predilection.

These sites generally include bifurcations, constrictions, dilation, or angulations of arteries. [1] Major risk factors for stroke are hypertension, heart disease, atherosclerosis, diabetes and elevated total blood cholesterol level. In patients with Acute Brain Injury, 70% have hypertension, 30% have

coronary heart disease, 30% have peripheral arterial disease, 15% have congestive heart disease, and 15% diabetes. Clinically, a variety of focal deficits are possible, including changes in the level of consciousness and impairments of sensory, motor, cognitive, perceptual, balance, speech and language functions. To be classified as stroke, neurological deficits must persist for at least 24 hours. [1]

Spasticity (hypertonicity) is a term, which was introduced to describe the velocity-sensitive increased resistance to a limb movement in subjects

with lesions of descending corticospinal pathways. [2] it is considered to be a part of positive signs of upper motor neuron (UMN) syndrome [3] and is a common disorder in patients with injury of the brain and spinal cord. Spasticity arises when the balance between inhibitory and excitatory fibres is disturbed i.e. either if the inhibitory pathways are interrupted or if there is increased activity in facilitatory pathways. [1,3,4] It occurs predominately in the anti-gravity muscles. In the upper extremity, the most frequent pattern of spasticity is scapular retraction; shoulder adduction, depression and internal rotation; elbow flexion and forearm pronation; and wrist and finger flexion. In the lower extremity, spasticity is often strong in the pelvic retraction, hip adduction, extension and internal rotation, knee extension, plantar flexion and supination, and toe flexion. [1] Measurement of spasticity can be done by clinical and laboratory methods. [2] Several scales have been developed and validated to assess spasticity in patients with brain injury. The two most commonly used scales are the Modified Ashworth Scale (MAS) and the Modified Tardieu Scale (MTS). [3] The Modified Tardieu Scale is differentiated into three parts:

1. Measures the passive range of motion described as: R2 at a stretching velocity as slow as possible (V1) R1 at a stretching velocity as fast as possible (V2).
2. Grades the quality of muscle reaction (X) to passive stretch at the fastest stretching velocity (V3).
3. Measures the angle of muscle reaction (Y) at the point of resistance to the fastest stretching velocity when the overactive stretch reflex produces a first catch (angle of muscle reaction- R1). [5]

V: Measurements Take Place At 3 Different Velocities:

V1- As slow as possible: Used to measure the passive range motion (PROM).

V2 -Speed of the limb segment falling under the effect of gravity

V3 -As fast as possible (> natural drop): Used to rate spasticity.

Y: Angle of catch (Quality of Muscle Reaction)

Spasticity Angle:

R1- Angle of catch seen at Velocity V3

R2- Full range of motion achieved when muscle is at rest and tested at V1 velocity

A large difference between R1 & R2 values in the outer to middle range of normal muscle length indicates a large dynamic component. A small difference in the R1 & R2 measurement in the middle to inner range indicates predominantly fixed contracture.

Electro diagnosis plays a critical role in the assessment of patients with spasticity. Techniques that register synaptic reflexes can be Electromyographical (EMG) responses such as the Hoffmann reflex (H-reflex) and F-wave and are the common neurophysiological evaluations used to measure spasticity. [3] The fraction of motor neuron pool activated in H-reflex is usually about 50% but can be as high as 100%. The ratio of peak-to-peak maximum H-reflex to peak to peak maximum M amplitude (Hmax/Mmax) provides an easy estimate of motor neuron pool activation, and therefore excitability. Although there is considerable variability of Hmax/Mmax ratio, Hmax/Mmax is normally less than 0.7. [6]

Methodology

To perform this study, study setting at Physiotherapy College was chosen. Data were collected from various physiotherapy centres in and around Rajkot city. A onetime observational study, purposive sampling with sample size of 32 subjects having stroke more than 3 months were considered.

The people with age 30-70 years, both male and female, had first episode of stroke and post stroke duration greater than 3 months, Unilateral involvement, a score of 2-6 on Brunnstrom stages of recovery for the upper limb and those able to understand and follow instructions for test procedure were involved for the study. The patients with previous history of stroke, abnormal upper limb movements before stroke, history of pain or surgery in affected upper limb, patients on any stimulant or relaxant medicines (including anti-spasticity and anti- convulsant, injections), inability to provide informed consent, diagnoses of any other neurological disorder or recent treatment that interfered with neuromuscular function, such as botulinum toxin injection were excluded from the study.

Examination Table / Plinth, Pillows, EMG-NCV Instrument (RMS EMG EP MK-II, Version 1.1), Bipolar Stimulating Electrode, Ground Electrode, Surface Electrodes, Electrode Gel, Adhesive tape, Spirit, Cotton, Universal 180° Standard Goniometer, Data collection sheet, Consent form, Pen and paper were the materials used for the study.

Figure 1: Materials Used In the Study

Figure 2: EMG-NCV Instrument

Figure 3: Treatment table

Methodology:

After the approval for the study from the ethical committee, 32 stroke patients who were diagnosed as having spasticity of wrist flexors of upper limb were selected for the study purpose from Out Patient Department (OPD) who fulfilled the inclusion and exclusion criteria. Mean age of stroke patients was 53.09+7.95 years. After proper

explanation about the purpose and procedure of the study, subjects who were willing to participate in the study were requested to sign a written consent form (Annexure 11.1).

The selection of subjects was done by purposive sampling. A pre-participation evaluation form (Annexure 11.2) consisting of basic neurological assessment chart was filled. The data measured

were recorded in the data collection form (Annexure 11.3) which included name, age, gender, dominance, side involved, post stroke duration, and Brunnstrom stage of recovery for the upper extremity.

All measurements have been taken in morning hours between 9:00 to 12:00. Before testing commencement, all patients have been asked to rest on the bed with shoes removed for 5 minutes and remain comfortable and relaxed. All the patients were asked to empty their bladder prior to testing. To provide a quiet testing environment, all tests have been performed in a close quiet room with natural light from windows.

The wrist flexors have been tested in this study, because they are usually spastic in post-stroke patients, and spasticity can be reliably measured in wrist flexors. [7,8] Outcome measures were Modified Tardieu Scale and Hmax/Mmax ratio. The sequence of testing was decided randomly by tossing a coin. The room was electrically shielded and earth grounded for H-reflex measurement. The H-reflex has been elicited in the FCR muscle of the affected side of the participants. The H-reflex in FCR muscle has been commonly employed in studies of H-reflex in the upper limb, and can be reliably evoked and measured.

Wrist flexors spasticity was assessed clinically on the affected side using MTS. For MTS, components of R1, R2, R2-R1 and quality of muscle reaction were measured. The electrophysiological data was also collected from the affected side. The motor nerve conduction study was performed first to get the maximum compound motor action potential and to get the best stimulating and recording site. In this study, Hmax/Mmax ratio was taken in 33 normal healthy individuals also in order to find normal value for Hmax/Mmax ratio in same age group and same population under similar testing conditions. Mean age of normal individuals was 48.78±7.90 years.

Method for motor nerve conduction study and H-reflex measurement:

- Position of patient: Supine lying, upper limb supported with elbow extended and forearm in supination.
- Electrode placement (As shown in figure 4)
- Recording active: Electrode is positioned over the belly of the flexor carpi radialis (FCR). This site is located at one-third distance from the medial epicondyle of humerus to the radial styloid process.
- Recording reference: Positioned over the brachioradialis muscle.
- Ground electrode: The ground electrode should be placed anywhere between stimulating and recording electrode.

Bipolar stimulating electrode: For motor nerve conduction study, the cathode is located over the median nerve at the antecubital fossa with anode proximal. By using Bipolar stimulating electrode, supramaximal stimulation is given over the median nerve until the maximum compound motor action potential (CMAP) is received.

Whereas for H-reflex measurement submaximal stimulation is given with anode distal with a pulse width of 0.5-1.0 ms is optimal and the current intensity is slowly increased until the H-reflex is maximized with an absent or minimally present FCR compound motor action potential (CMAP).

Instrumentation Parameters for motor nerve conduction study:

- Sweep speed: 5 ms/div
- Sensitivity: 200-500
- Filter setting: 5hz- 3 KHz

Instrumentation Parameters for H-reflex measurement:

- Sweep speed: 10ms/div
- Sensitivity: 200-500 μ v/div
- Filter setting: 3 KHz

Figure 4: Placement of Electrodes for Hmax/Mmax Ratio Flexor Carpi Radialis

Figure 5: Measurement of wrist extension ROM for MTS

Method for modified tardieu scale:

Subjects were placed in supine lying with wrist joint in neutral position with elbow in extension. As shown in figure 5, the goniometer was fixed by placing the Centre of the goniometer on the lateral aspect of the wrist over the triquetrum. The proximal arm was aligned with the lateral midline of the ulna, using the olecranon and ulnar styloid process for reference. The distal arm was aligned with the lateral midline of the fifth metacarpal. [9]

First, the wrist joint was moved in extension with a fast-stretching velocity (V3) and the angle of catch (R1) was noted. After this the wrist joint was moved in extension with a very slow-stretching velocity (V1) from neutral position to measure the passive range of motion (PROM). During this maneuver, the catch was noted as R2. Quality of muscle reaction component ranging from 0 to 4 grades was also recorded.

Results

Table 1: Age distribution of stroke patients and normal subjects

Age Group (Years)	No. of Stroke Subjects		No. of Normal Subjects	
	N	%	N	%
35-40	2	6	6	18
41-45	5	16	5	15
46-50	5	16	7	22
51-55	4	12	7	21
56-60	11	34	6	18
61-65	4	13	2	6
66-70	1	3	0	0
TOTAL	32		33	

Figure 6: Age Distribution in (a) Stroke patients, (b) Normal subjects

Interpretation: The above figure and table show number of subjects and their percentage age distribution.

Table 2: Mean Age and SD for stroke patients and normal subjects

Group	N	Minimum (Years)	Maximum (Years)	Mean (Years)	Sd (Years)
Stroke patients	32	36	66	53.1	7.95
Normal subjects	33	36	65	48.78	7.90

Figure 7: Bar Diagram for Mean Age and SD in stroke patients and Normal subjects

Interpretation: The table displays the statistics of age distribution of the 32 stroke patients and 33 normal subjects. The mean + SD of age of 32 stroke subjects was 53.1 ± 7.95 years and for 33 normal individuals 48.78 + 7.90 years.

Table 3: Gender Distribution in stroke patients and normal subjects

Gender	Stroke patients		Normal subjects	
	N	%	N	%
Male	25	78	9	27
Female	7	22	24	73
Total	32		33	

Figure 8: Gender Distribution. (a) Stroke patients, (b) Normal subjects

Interpretation: The above figure and table show percentage distribution of gender.

Table 4: Result of Pearson correlation coefficient showing correlation between Dynamic angle component of Modified Tardieu Scale and Hmax/Mmax ratio

Measure	Pearson Correlation Coefficient (r value)	p value	No. of patients (N)
Dynamic angle component and Hmax/Mmax ratio	-0.196	0.2	32

Figure 9: Result of Pearson correlation coefficient showing correlation between Dynamic angle component of Modified Tardieu Scale and Hmax/Mmax ratio

Interpretation: Pearson correlation coefficient (rp) between Dynamic angle component of Modified Tardieu Scale and Hmax/Mmax ratio is -0.196 with p = 0.2. Above table shows moderately negative correlation between Dynamic angle component of Modified Tardieu Scale and Hmax/Mmax ratio.

Table 5: Result of Spearman’s correlation coefficient showing correlation between Quality of muscle reaction component of Modified Tardieu Scale and Hmax/Mmax ratio

Measure	Spearman Correlation Coefficient (r value)	p value	No. of patients (N)
Quality of muscle reaction and Hmax/Mmax ratio	0.338	0.05	32

Figure 10: Result of Spearman’s correlation coefficient showing correlation between Quality of muscle reaction component of Modified Tardieu Scale and Hmax/Mmax ratio

Interpretation: Spearman correlation coefficient (rs) between Quality of muscle reaction component of Modified Tardieu Scale and Hmax/Mmax ratio is .338 with $p = .05$ (p value = 0.05). Above table shows moderately positive correlation between Quality of muscle reaction component of Modified Tardieu Scale and Hmax/Mmax ratio.

Table 6: Result of Unpaired-t test for comparison of Hmax/Mmax ratio of Stroke patients and Normal subjects

Groups	Mean	+SD	No. Of Subjects	T- Value	P- Value	Result
Stroke patients	0.80	0.31	32	3.517	0.001	Significant
Normal healthy individuals	0.59	0.12	33			

Figure 11: Comparison between Hmax/Mmax ratio of stroke patients and normal subjects

Interpretation: Unpaired-t test for comparison between Hmax/Mmax ratio of stroke patients and normal individual is 3.517 with p value is 0.001 ($p < 0.05$). Above table suggesting highly statistical significantly increase in Hmax/Mmax ratio in stroke patients as compare to normal subjects.

Discussion

In the above study it was found that there is moderately negative correlation between Dynamic angle component of Modified Tardieu Scale and Hmax/Mmax ratio. And there is a moderately positive correlation between Quality of muscle reaction component of Modified Tardieu Scale and Hmax/Mmax ratio. Thus, the results of the present study reject the null hypothesis and support the experimental hypothesis i.e. there is correlation between modified Tardieu scale and Hmax/Mmax ratio in the assessment of wrist flexor spasticity in the patients with chronic stroke.

Modified Tardieu Scale is taken as a clinical tool to assess wrist flexors spasticity in patients with chronic stroke because it is reliable tool to assess spasticity. Hmax/Mmax ratio can provide quantitative parameters to assess spasticity which can be helpful in research purpose also and can give exact quantity of spasticity also and it is a

reliable tool to assess spasticity. In this study, to see the effect of spasticity on Hmax/Mmax ratio, Hmax/Mmax ratio was taken in normal healthy individual in same age group and result suggested that there is marked increased in Hmax/Mmax ratio in hemiplegic side as compared to normal healthy individuals. The results of this study confirm an increase in the mean values of the Hmax/Mmax ratio in the spastic muscle. However, there were marked variations between same degrees of hypertonia. The Hmax/Mmax ratio was higher in patients who scored 2 on quality of muscle reaction component of Modified Tardieu Scale than in those who scored 1. So, there is a moderately positive correlation between the quality of muscle reaction component of Modified Tardieu scale and Hmax/Mmax ratio.

Conclusion

From the present study it can be concluded that Modified Tardieu Scale can be used to assess spasticity in clinical practice as it fulfils the velocity dependent definition of spasticity given by Lance.

It can also be concluded that Hmax/Mmax ratio can also be used to assess spasticity and it is quantifying the spasticity and its correlation with

MTS suggests that both tools of spasticity measurement can be used as an alternative to each other in the assessment of wrist flexors spasticity in the patients with chronic stroke. This protocol utilizes conventional and new indicators of motor neuron excitability in spasticity for comparative validity evaluation. Further, the protocol utilizes standard methodology for spasticity assessment to indicate the excitability of the α motor neuron pool.

References

1. O'Sullivan SB, Schmitz TJ. Physical Rehabilitation. 5th edition. New Delhi: Jaypee Brothers; 2007.
2. Singh P, Joshua AM, Ganeshan S, Suresh S. Intra-Rater Reliability of The Modified Tardieu Scale to Quantify Spasticity in Elbow Flexors and Ankle Plantar Flexors in Adult Stroke Subjects. *Ann Indian Acad Neurol* 2011 Jan-Mar; 14(1): 23–6.
3. Thibaut A, Chatelle C, Ziegler E, Laureys S, Gosseries O. Spasticity after stroke: Physiology, assessment and treatment. *Brain Inj.* 2013;1–13.
4. Nielsen JB, Crone C, Hultborn H. The Spinal Pathophysiology of Spasticity – From A Basic Science Point of View. *Acta Physiol* 2007, 189:171–80.
5. Mehrholz J, Wagner K, Meisner D, Grundman K, Zange C, Pohl M. Reliability of The Modified Tardieu Scale and The Modified Ashworth Scale in Adult Patients with Severe Brain Injury: A Comparison Study. *Clin Rehabil* 2005; 19:751-59.
6. U.K. Mishra & J. Kalita; *Clinical neurophysiology*; 3rd edition; Elsevier; 2014:97-101.
7. Naghdi S, Ansari NN, Azarnia S, et al. Interrater reliability of the Modified Modified Ashworth Scale (MMAS) for patients with wrist flexor muscle spasticity. *Physiotherapy Theory & Practical* 2008; 24:372–9.
8. Ansari NN, Naghdi S, Hasson S, et al. Assessing the reliability of the Modified Modified Ashworth Scale between two physiotherapists in adult patients with hemiplegia. *Neuro-Rehabilitation* 2009; 25:235–40.
9. Kai S, Nakabayashi. Evoked EMG Makes Measurement of Muscle Tone Possible by Analysis of the H/M Ratio. *Electrodiagnosis in New Frontiers of Clinical Research*.